

THE IMPACT OF RHYTHMIC GYMNASTICS ON THE PHYSICAL HEALTH AND DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN AND ADOLESCENTS

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Annotation

Rhythmic gymnastics is a set of exercises aimed at developing flexibility, coordination and musicality in children and adolescents. This article provides an overview of research on the impact of rhythmic gymnastics on the physical health and development of young people. The main mechanisms of the impact of this sport on the body are analyzed, including physical development, maintaining health, improving coordination and balance, as well as psychological aspects of training. The obtained data make it possible to identify the importance of rhythmic gymnastics in the formation of a full-fledged physical and emotional state of children and adolescents.

Keywords: rhythmic gymnastics, children, adolescents, physical health, development, coordination, musicality, psychological well-being.

Introduction. Rhythmic gymnastics is a unique sport that includes elements of choreography, flexibility and working with various projectiles accompanied by music. This sport not only promotes the development of physical qualities, but also has a positive effect on the emotional and psychological state of children and adolescents. Rhythmic gymnastics requires athletes to have a high

level of coordination, flexibility and endurance, which makes it attractive to young people of various ages and physical fitness. In this article, we will review the results of research on the impact of rhythmic gymnastics on the physical health and development of young people, as well as analyze the key aspects of this sport in the context of its impact on the physical and psychological well-being of children and adolescents.

Methods. To analyze the impact of rhythmic gymnastics on the physical health and development of children and adolescents, data from a number of scientific studies conducted in recent decades were used. Both qualitative and quantitative studies covering various aspects of the impact of this sport on the body of young people were considered. Methods of meta-analysis and systematic review of scientific literature were used to compare the effectiveness of rhythmic gymnastics. As a result, the main trends and patterns of the influence of rhythmic gymnastics on the physical and emotional state of children and adolescents were identified.

Results. Research results show that rhythmic gymnastics exercises have a positive effect on the physical health and development of children and adolescents. In particular, regular training helps to improve flexibility, strength and endurance, as well as the development of movement coordination and balance. Research also shows that rhythmic gymnastics helps to improve the psychological well-being of young people. Participation in this form of physical activity is associated with increased self-esteem, self-discipline and self-confidence in children and adolescents. These results highlight the importance of integrating rhythmic gymnastics into educational and rehabilitation programs for children with developmental disabilities, in order to achieve optimal results on both physical and emotional levels.

Conclusions. Research confirms the importance of rhythmic gymnastics in the development of physical health and emotional well-being of children and

adolescents. This sport provides a unique opportunity not only to improve physical fitness, but also to develop coordination, flexibility and musicality among young people. Regular rhythmic gymnastics workouts contribute to the formation of a healthy lifestyle among children and adolescents, and also help to increase the level of self-confidence and self-discipline. Thus, the inclusion of rhythmic gymnastics in educational programs and extracurricular activities can be an important step in ensuring the full-fledged physical and emotional development of the younger generation.

List of used literature

1. Xaitbayeva, B. (2024). THE ROLE AND METHODS OF TEACHING RHYTHMIC GYMNASTICS IN SCHOOL PHYSICAL EDUCATION. *European Journal of Pedagogical Initiatives and Educational Practices*, 2(1), 23-26.
2. Xaitbayeva, B. (2024). RHYTHMIC GYMNASTICS: INTEGRATION INTO THE PHYSICAL EDUCATION CURRICULUM. *European Journal of Pedagogical Initiatives and Educational Practices*, 2(1), 15-18.
3. Хайтбаева, Б. Б. (2023). РИТМИЧЕСКАЯ ГИМНАСТИКА КАК СРЕДСТВО ЭСТЕТИЧЕСКОГО ВОСПИТАНИЯ. *IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI*, 3(33), 142-146.
4. Bahodirovna, K. B. (2023). Improving the System of Professional Training of Future Teachers Using Musical Rhythmic Gymnastics (Using the Example of Physical Education Teachers). *American Journal of Language, Literacy and Learning in STEM Education (2993-2769)*, 1(8), 13-18.
5. Bakhodirovna, K. B. (2023). RESEARCH OF MORPHOLOGICAL FEATURES AND PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF YOUTH. *Global Book Publishing Services*, 1-99.

6. Хаитбаева, Б. (2023). СОДЕРЖАНИЯ УПРАЖНЕНИЙ РИТМИЧЕСКОЙ ГИМНАСТИКИ С ЭЛЕМЕНТАМИ КЛАССИЧЕСКОЙ АЭРОБИКИ. *IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI*, 3(27), 110-115.

7. Хаитбаева, Б. (2023). ВОЗДЕЙСТВИЕ РИТМИЧЕСКОЙ ГИМНАСТИКИ НА ОРГАНИЗМ ЗАНИМАЮЩИХСЯ. *Finland International Scientific Journal of Education. Social Science & Humanities*, 11(3), 1079-1084.

8. Bakhodirovna, K. B., & Kayumovna, R. M. (2022). Formation of motor culture of students in the lessons of rhythmic gymnastics. *INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876*, 16(10), 118-124.

9. Bahodirovna, X. B. (2022). The use of rhythmic gymnastics in the practice of school physical education teachers on the example of the city of fergana. *International Journal of Pedagogics*, 2(05), 1-4.

10. Bahodirovna, X. B., & Ilxomjonovich, I. I. (2022). *The use of Rhythmic Gymnastics in the Physical Education of Schoolchildren on the Example of the City of Fergana. International Journal of Pedagogics*, 2(05), 9-12.

11. Skuratovich, V., & Hadasevic, O. (2020). *PHYSICAL EDUCATION IN THE STRUCTURE OF PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION. Anatoly Batyan, Sergei Golovatiy, Mikalay Plavinski*, 25.

12. Tulanovich, Y. T., Madaminovich, D. E., & Baxodirovna, X. B. (2021). *Rhythmic gymnastics in the system of physical education. Innovative Technologica: Methodical Research Journal*, 2(12), 25-29.

13. Аветисян К.А. *Психологическое содержание и условия развития поведенческой гибкости учителя: Автореф. дис. ... канд. психол. наук. – М., 3. 2001.*

14. *Акмеология / Под ред. А.А.Деркача. – М.: РАГС, 2002.*

15. Геннадиевна, К. Г., И Гильфановна, К. С. (2022). Средства и методы формирования у учащихся положительного отношения к физическим упражнениям. Международный журнал исследований в области коммерции, информационных технологий, инженерии и социальных наук ISSN: 2349-7793 Импакт-фактор: 6.876, 16(10), 133-139.

16. Козлова, Г. Г. (2022). Самоконтроль занимающихся физической культурой и спортом. Ijodkor o'qituvchi, 2(24), 22-29.

17. Геннадьевна, К. Г. (2021). Легкая атлетика в системе физического воспитания студенческой молодежи. На междисциплинарной конференции молодых ученых в области социальных наук (стр. 143-145).

18. Козлова, Г. Г. (2023). Инновационные образовательные технологии в повышении профессионального спортивно-педагогического мастерства студентов. O'zbekistonda fanlararo innovatsiyalar va ilmiy tadqiqotlar jurnali, 2(19), 38-42.

19. Козлова, Г. (2024). ФИЗИЧЕСКАЯ АКТИВНОСТЬ И ПСИХИЧЕСКОЕ ЗДОРОВЬЕ: НЕВИДИМЫЕ СВЯЗИ, ОЧЕВИДНЫЕ ВЫГОДЫ. Молодые ученые, 2(2), 10-15.

20. Козлова, Г. (2024). ПРОПАГАНДА И РАЗВИТИЕ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ И МАССОВОГО СПОРТА. Бюллетень педагогов нового Узбекистана, 2(1), 35-39.

21. Козлова, Г. Г. (2024). РОЛЬ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ В ПОДДЕРЖАНИИ ОБЩЕГО ЗДОРОВЬЯ. THE ROLE OF SCIENCE AND INNOVATION IN THE MODERN WORLD, 3(1), 5-13.

22. . Козлова, Г. Г. (2023). ПЕДАГОГИКО-ПСИХОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ВОЛЕВЫХ КАЧЕСТВ У БУДУЩИХ ПРЕПОДАВАТЕЛЕЙ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ КУЛЬТУРЫ. Innovation in the modern education system, 3(30), 199-204

23. Козлова, Г. (2024). ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИХ ПОДХОДОВ К ОЦЕНКЕ УРОВНЯ ФИЗИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВЛЕННОСТИ СТУДЕНТОВ В ТЕЧЕНИЕ ПОСЛЕДНИХ ДЕСЯТИ ЛЕТ. В THEORETICAL ASPECTS IN THE FORMATION OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES (Т. 3, Выпуск 3, с. 32–37).